

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most typical is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear and then the polar bear. Found throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Could be darkish or light brown (cinnamon), typically even white. Not all the time black in colour. 900,000 and never threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear will be found throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nevertheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected under the U.S. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to 6 feet in length. □□ Options: Most black bears are black, but their fur can vary from darkish brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on rare events. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are a few of the perfect at climbing bushes. Their relatively smaller dimension and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb bushes for protection, meals, and even hibernation. The vast majority of their food regimen is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Food regimen: Their different food regimen provides them the ability to dwell in a big range of habitats. Additionally they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They are the almost certainly bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And yes, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the 2 subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center [pooh teddy bear online](#) East. Brown bears are the most widespread of all bear species, discovered in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are accountable for nearly all bear assaults in North America, with forty six per 12 months. Though their conservation status is "least concern", their unfold-out nature and decreased habitat make lots of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large construct, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the guidelines, which led to the title of essentially the most well-known subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt younger mammals equivalent to elk and moose. Their colour varies from gentle blonde to dark brown. The 2 subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are discovered in the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh 400 to 790 pounds, are 6.5 ft lengthy, and have a shoulder peak of 3.3 ft. □□ Weight loss program: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been recognized to prey on large mammals. Coastal grizzlies are usually bigger than these discovered in the Rocky Mountains resulting from a richer diet. Annually there are 46 assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Identified for his or her aggressive conduct, grizzlies are answerable for probably the most bear assaults in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only found on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Dimension: Kodiak bears are virtually as massive as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, 8 feet lengthy, and four ft tall on the shoulder. □□ Food regimen: Their eating regimen is just like mainland grizzly bears. Nevertheless, because of extra plentiful meals sources, the islands can support a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to develop into their very own subspecies. This has led to a more advanced social structure which results in much less conflict between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears can be aggressive. As a result of their isolation, there is just one attack on humans each other year. Largest species of bear on this planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Weight loss program is usually made up of meat, usually from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the largest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur appears white however is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary in the snow-lined arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and may be 7 to 10 feet tall. They're a threatened species attributable to lack of habitat from local weather change. Despite their huge dimension polar bears can be fast, maintaining a 6 mph pace within the water. □□ Features: Compared to different bears, polar bears have a slimmer physique, slim head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Eating regimen: Their weight loss program consists mostly of animals, especially seals which they can odor from a mile away. Although they seem white, their fur is definitely clear and their pores and skin is black. □□ Harmful? Polar bears can be extremely harmful. They see people as potential prey. Assaults are rare as a result of distant nature of their habitat. Known for its cream colour chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Straightforward to tame and sometimes widespread in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is present in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account weak. □□ Dimension: One of the smaller species, adults weigh around 300 pounds and stand forty seven to 75 inches tall. □□ Diet: Depending on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds,

insects, and honey. Assaults on humans are growing as folks encroach on their habitat. ☐☐ Harmful? They're certainly one of the simplest bears to tame (and therefore common in circuses), but Asian black bears are more aggressive than their North American counterparts. Discovered only in China. 99% of its weight loss program is bamboo. In truth, the second particular person in historical past to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas protecting his sheep. Identified for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. ☐☐Location: Pandas are found only in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 stay within the wild and they're thought of a vulnerable species. ☐☐ Dimension: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and might be over four toes tall, a powerful feat considering they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at birth. It also has an in depth cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical pattern in light brown and white. ☐☐ Food plan: Unlike other bears the panda's food plan is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. ☐☐ Features: The large panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped physique. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them common: they poop over 40 instances a day! ☐☐ Dangerous? Attacks are rare but harmful, on condition that pandas have one in every of the very best bite forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch long tongue for slurping up insects and honey. ☐☐Location: The Solar bear is discovered within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is uncertain however thought-about susceptible and on the decline resulting from lack of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for his or her gallbladders and other physique elements utilized in conventional medicines. ☐☐ Measurement: They stand solely 39 to 55 inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. ☐☐ Features: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They're named for his or her pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that appears like a rising sun. They also eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. ☐☐ Weight loss program: Solar bears tear apart timber and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In actual fact, they have an incredibly lengthy tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. ☐☐ Dangerous? Attributable to its shy nature, attacks are uncommon. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the identify sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. ☐☐Location: The Sloth bear is discovered within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of less than 20,000, they are thought-about susceptible. ☐☐ Dimension: They're fifty five to 75 inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. ☐☐ Options: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they're easy to tell other than other Asiatic bears. In reality, they're very fast and might out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging upside down from bushes. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their large curved claws. ☐☐ Food plan: Their food regimen consists of termites, ants, and fruit. ☐☐ Dangerous? They're some of the aggressive bears, with the most attacks on humans, largely resulting from surprise encounters. They blow the mud round with massive puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 feet away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and don't combine well with rhinos and elephants, often charging at one another when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's last brief-faced bear. The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that look like glasses. This vulnerable species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are discovered within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. ☐☐ Size: They're mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to 79 inches tall. ☐☐Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last short-faced bear and the one bear native to South America. ☐☐ Options: The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that sometimes appear like glasses. They spend most of their time in trees where they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard valuable fruit and carcasses. ☐☐ Weight loss program: Spectacled bears are mostly herbivores with a diet consisting of largely cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they are going to opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. ☐☐ Dangerous? Living in distant mountains, these shy bears often is the least harmful of all bear species. Their bodies are smaller than polar bears however larger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear habits is closer to the polar bear. They function the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, much like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably on the London Zoo in 1859, but have not been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot but DNA tests were unable to determine what sort of bear it was. Adorable koalas usually are not bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears either, they're indestructible, microscopic animals that may survive in space. Most bear attacks occur when a bear is startled or defending their cubs. Red pandas? They're in their very own household which might be closer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR

SURROUNDINGS. Watch for bear scat and bear tracks that will indicate a bear is nearby, wherein case you want to be extra vigilant. Here are a few tips you need to use to forestall bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies protected. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you are right here so they don't unintentionally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** Whereas you may have nice intentions, a bear is more likely to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Gadgets (AT CAMP).** For those who see a bear, do not try to strategy or feed it. This includes meals, but also your toiletries, for example. Whichever technique you choose, ensure that it's at least 200 toes away from your tent so you don't appeal to bears to your campsite. 4. **Stay CALM.** In case you meet a bear, do not run. Attempt to make yourself look as massive as doable, waving your arms above your head. You can too lengthen a jacket above your head to make yourself look bigger. Lock these things in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hang them up in a tree. Don't scream or try to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT).** Communicate to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously close (30 feet) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward. 6. **Fight Back.** If all else fails and a bear assaults you, do not play useless. Which bear is the most important? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 ft long, and 4.0 to 5.25 feet tall, the biggest bear by each measurement and weight is the polar bear. The most important ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Combat again with all your energy and hope that it will back down. Which bear is probably the most harmful? All bears are harmful if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is thought for essentially the most attacks. When in bear nation, it's at all times wise to carry bear spray. It's well deserved, especially when cubs are around. Each year there are roughly forty six grizzly assaults, 6 leading to death. In North America, grizzly bears have the most fearsome popularity. Which bear is the strongest? While you're most prone to see an American black bear, on average there is just one attack per yr. In terms of uncooked bite power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chew reigns supreme. All bears are robust and not to be messed with. When utilizing the chunk power quotient (chew power relative to measurement), the sun bear packs probably the most punch. Originally named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub discovered in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the fireplace however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he turned an icon and to this day is the star of the longest-operating public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear identified for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has inspired numerous through-hikers to try and master the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not fairly begging however receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, although he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a responsibility-free way of life. He additionally may be the first bear to obtain his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son often would go to at the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the town in Canada near the place he was from. Chris also wrote How to Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal parts backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After thru-hiking the Appalachian Trail, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to offer fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic tips, guides and how-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

